

Transitioning from Preclinical to Clinical Training: An Evaluation of Students' Challenges and Adaptation Strategies

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ABSTRACT

Dental college is a rigorous professional path that includes preclinical skill development, clinical competency, and theoretical instruction. Students encounter a variety of academic, clinical, and psychological obstacles during their formative first year and the demanding internship phase. **Objective** - The daily challenges faced by dentistry students at all five academic levels—first, second, third, final, and internship are examined in this cross-sectional questionnaire-based study. **Material and methods** - 450 participants from Jkkndch were given a validated survey. **Result** - According to the findings, the most often mentioned problems were exam pressure, clinical stress, and academic overload. While interns dealt with workload and anxiety related to patient management, first-year students primarily suffered with adaptability and theoretical volume. **conclusion** - The study emphasizes the necessity of stress management techniques, mentorship programs, and academic support networks.

Keywords: Transitioning, Preclinical to Clinical Training, Students' Challenges, Adaptation Strategies, Dental college

INTRODUCTION

Overview Students must learn biological sciences, manual dexterity, and patient-centered care as part of the rigorous academic and technical requirements of dental school. Every academic year brings with it its own set of difficulties: **First Year:** Anatomy, physiology, and biochemistry are covered as you go from classroom instruction to professional education. **Second Year:** Deeper theoretical understanding through preclinical lab work in prosthodontics, pathology, and microbiology. **Third Year:** Theory and patient care are balanced as clinical exposure begins. **Final Year:** Academic pressure, clinical quota completion, and thorough case handling. **Internship:** Clinical independence, practical patient care, and career readiness. To enhance dental education curriculum design, academic planning, and student well-being, it is crucial to comprehend how difficulties change during the course of the course.

Goals

1. until determining the clinical, academic, and psychological challenges that dental students encounter from their first year until their internship.
2. To compare the type and degree of stress experienced during various academic years.
3. To suggest tactics that support students' emotional fortitude, clinical proficiency, and adaptability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Undergraduate dentistry students in a cross-sectional descriptive research using questionnaires.

Participants

450 dental students in all were chosen at random:

First Year: 55
Second Year: 100
Third Year: 100
Final Year: 100
Internships: 95

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Data Gathering Instrument

Subject matter experts created and verified a 20-item structured questionnaire.

It addressed:

- Stress from exams
- workload for preclinical and clinical
- Peer assistance and interactions with faculty
- Communication and treatment of patients
- Both physical and mental health

METHODOLOGY

A total of 450 participants we are taken a questionnaire based response in dental students.

According to the findings, the most often mentioned

problems were exam pressure, clinical stress, and academic overload. While interns dealt with workload and anxiety related to patient management, first-year students primarily suffered with adaptability and theoretical volume

Statistical analysis

Interpretation: Out of 20 questions analyzed, 15 showed statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between students and interns. These indicate that response patterns for these questions differ meaningfully across groups by an chi square test was performed using SPSS software version 21.

RESULTS

Category	Findings
Major Sources of Stress	Case completion (78%), Time management (74%), Exams (69%),
Difficulty Balancing Theory & Clinicals	64% reported 'Difficult' or 'Often challenging'
Completing Case Requirements	70% struggle 'Often' or 'Sometimes'
Clinical Exposure Satisfaction	55% satisfied, 35% neutral, 10% dissatisfied
Confidence Before Procedures	58% reported occasional lack of confidence
Supervision & Faculty Support	60% 'Satisfied' or 'Very Satisfied'; 25% neutral
Difficulty Getting Patients	48% face difficulty 'Often'
Burnout / Fatigue Levels	63% experience burnout 'Often' or 'Sometimes'
Academic Overload Stress	72% 'Often stressed' due to academic work
Anxiety Before Clinical Work	59% experience anxiety 'Sometimes' or 'Often'
Time Management Rating	68% rated 'Neutral to Poor'
Work-Life Balance / Well-being	62% find it 'Difficult' to maintain a healthy routine
Overall Satisfaction (Clinical Learning)	57% satisfied, 22% neutral, 21% dissatisfied

Chi square	P value
265.00	.0000
26.20	.0001
265.00	.0000
9.95	.0413
8.47	.0372
118.70	.0000
265.00	.0000
6.67	.0355
18.09	.0012
265.00	.0000
1.41	.8430
47.06	.0000
104.05	.0000
262.04	.0000
247.61	.0000

DISCUSSION

There is a trend of rising academic and clinical stress as dentistry school progresses. Later years concentrate on clinical responsibilities and patient care, while early years are dominated by theoretical overload. The main stressors in dentistry education include workload, time limits, and performance anxiety. Despite being intended for hands-on learning, the internship term frequently becomes too demanding because of the demands of handling cases independently and meeting quotas. The necessity of a structured mentorship program that offers individualized support according to a student's educational stage is emphasized by this study.

CONCLUSION

Throughout their academic careers, dental students encounter a range of challenges. Adaptation and academic volume are challenges in the early stages (first and second years). Stress from clinical learning and theoretical balance throughout the mid-phase (third and final year). Internship: Limited emotional support and maximum responsibility. Promoting a healthy learning environment requires frequent stress audits, candid faculty communication, and focused counseling sessions.

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